

THE BEHAVIOUR OF DRIVEN TUBULAR STEEL PILES IN THE LAMINATED MUDSTONES OF SOUTH WEST IRELAND

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Synopsis

This paper describes the experiences gained during the installation of tubular steel piles into laminated mudstones for two jetty projects in south-west Ireland.

A feature of the pile driving, for the Moneypoint Jetty in Co. Clare, was the development of a "false set" as shown by a reduction in resistance to driving. Following three pile test failures an extensive programme of investigation, research and testing was carried out which resulted in piling operations being held up for 3 months. Pile redriving was carried out and 142 No. of the piles were redriven by up to 3.1m.

As the results of rock coring at about 135 locations and the results of an extensive programme of laboratory tests were already available, the bedrock could be categorised into 4 different zones depending on the rock type, its strength and fracture state. It was shown that the piles which required redriving and which failed the load test were mostly confined to one of the 4 zones.

The paper describes the geology of the site, the design and construction of the piles, the problems encountered and the subsequent remedial action. Some possible explanations are given to the reasons for the development of the "false set" and for the load test failures.

The lessons learned at Moneypoint were applied to the design and construction of the foundation for Keelbeg Pier at Union Hall in West Cork. The pile installation procedure specified was based on the experiences from Moneypoint.

FIGURE 1: VIEW OF MONEYPPOINT JETTY DURING PILING WORKS

Glenbeigh Records
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1.0 INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the site investigation, design and construction of the pile foundations for two jetties in South West Ireland. Some difficulties were encountered during the piling for a large coal unloading jetting at Moneypoint Power Station in Co. Clare. The experience gained at Moneypoint was used in the pile design for a fishing jetty, known as Keelbeg Pier at Union Hall in West Cork. The location of the two sites is shown on Figure 2.

Moneypoint Jetty was designed by the Electricity Supply Board (ESB) Civil Works Department (now ESB International) with Rendel Palmer Tritton (RPT) as consultant advisers. The jetty was constructed by a joint venture of Ascon Ltd. of Ireland and HBM of Holland. ESB appointed Soil Mechanics Ltd. (SML) to advise them on various aspects of the site investigation and the piling works. The design and construction of the jetty has previously been described in a paper by O'Connor and Greene (1986, Ref. 1). A study of the jetty during piling operations is shown on Figure 1.

Keelbeg Pier was designed by ESB International Ltd. (ESBI) for the Department of the Marine. The jetty was constructed by John Fleming Construction Ltd. of Cork. A geological consultant, Carraigex Ltd. of Cork City was appointed by Flemings to advise them on further site investigation works. A view of Keelbeg Pier during piling works is shown on Figure 8.

FIGURE 2 : KEY PLAN - SHOWING LOCATIONS OF JETTIES

2.0 MONEYPOINT JETTY - INITIAL INVESTIGATION AND DESIGN

2.1 Initial Site Investigations

The initial investigation for Moneypoint Jetty began in 1978 with an echo sounding survey, a study of tidal streams, an investigation of the sea bed by divers and a geophysical survey using continuous seismic refraction profiling. In 1979 Nutall Geotechnical Services carried out an offshore site investigation, which comprised 15 rotary cored boreholes, to a maximum depth of 30m below the sea bed.

2.2 Geology

The investigation revealed the following succession of strata:

Stratum	Thickness (m)
Recent Estuarine Deposits (Loose sand overlying soft silty clay)	Zero to 13.9, Average 5.2
Glacial Deposits (Very stiff to hard silty clay with gravels and cobbles, coarse fraction increases with depth)	4.7 to 14.8 Average 7.7
Bedrock (see below)	14 max. proven

Table 1: Moneypoint Site Geology from Initial Site Investigation

In 13 of the 15 boreholes the bedrock comprised a faintly to slightly weathered dark grey, moderately strong to strong mudstone. In the remaining 2 boreholes the bedrock consisted of a faintly weathered strong to very strong sandstone. Within the upper 3m, the mudstone had an RQD value of 20% to 80% with an average of about 50% and a mean fracture spacing of 60mm to 150mm. The mudstone had a conservative average unconfined compressive strength (UCS) of 25MN/m². The corresponding value for the sandstone was in excess of 100MN/m².

2.3 Pile Design

The piles are of open ended tubular steel construction with an outside diameter of 1220mm, and a wall thickness of 19mm in Grade 43A mild steel. The pile toe has a wall thickness of 30mm over a length of about 1m with the exterior of this reinforced section flush with the main body of the pile.

Pile design was based on the assumption that the piles would obtain their load carrying capacity entirely in end bearing on the mudstone bedrock. The ultimate bearing capacity of the mudstone was taken as 6 x UCS, after Rehnman and Broms (1971, Ref 2) and Ladanyi (1971, Ref 3), giving an allowable load capacity of 600t. This gives a pile wall steel stress of about 85N/mm², which is well within the allowable stress for Grade 43A steel.

The Specification required the Contractor to determine rock level in each area before piling began and that the piles should "be driven into sound bedrock to the ultimate driving resistance of 750t calculated by the Hiley Formula". This calculation yielded a design "set" of about 40 blows/50mm. The Contract allowed for a number of static load tests. No re-driving of the piles was specified at the outset of the Contract because the mudstones had been assessed as moderately strong. It would only have been common practice to specify re-driving in weak rocks.

2.4 Driving Trials

Four open ended tubular steel piles, of outside diameter 760mm and wall thickness 16mm were installed in a trial driving exercise in 1979. Two were driven using a Delmag D60 hammer and two using a Menck MRB 1000 hammer. No particular problems were encountered in driving these piles into bedrock. Two piles were subsequently extracted and the one which had been driven without toe reinforcing was found to be damaged. The performance of the hammers was similar.

2.5 Jetty Structure

The final design configuration of the jetty comprised a 380m long 33m wide structure, which is supported on 425 open ended tubular steel piles. The jetty has two mooring dolphins, one at either end. A view of the jetty structure during construction is shown on Figure 1 and the jetty layout is shown on Figure 3. Strong-points have been incorporated into the jetty at three locations by the provision of raking piles in addition to the grid of vertical piles. The minimum water depth at the jetty is 25m.

The jetty was designed to support three 1200t coal unloaders and a live load of 15kN/m². The jetty is also designed to resist lateral loads imposed by a 275,000 dwt bulk carrier.

FIGURE 3 : LAYOUT OF MONEYPPOINT COAL UNLOADING JETTY

3.0 MONEYPPOINT JETTY - PILING DIFFICULTIES

3.1 October 1981 to July 1982

Piling began at the east end of the jetty in October 1981. The piles were driven from a jack-up barge using a HERA 7500 diesel hammer. The hammer had a weight of 7500kg and a nominal rated energy of 20,700 kgm per blow at a rate of 40 blows per minute. The ram to pile weight ratio was about 0.3.

Pile driving began at Bent Nos 67 to 70 in the eastern strong-point, see Figure 3. The driving records show negligible resistance in the estuarine deposits and the upper layers of the glacial deposits. Resistance increased to 5 to 10 blows/50mm towards the base of this stratum and then increased fairly rapidly in the bedrock. Between pile Bent Nos 60 to 30 the piles were driven to sets of between 42 and 55 blows/50 mm. A successful load test to 750t was carried out on Pile 68D, in the eastern strong-point, which is founded in sandstone. All piles were braced temporarily until fixed in the complete structure.

3.1 Cont....

FIGURE 4 : LOAD TESTS ON PILES 30D, 38E AND 42E

After a storm on 14 December 1981, when oscillation of the piles took place, seven piles between Bent Nos 68 and 73 were redriven. The piles were driven by up to a further 70mm before achieving the design set.

Piling then continued until Pile 30D on the central strong-point failed during a load test in July 1982, at about 725t, see Figure 4. Plastic yielding of the ground beneath the toe appears to have begun at about 450t. The pile was redriven the following day and subsequently load tested successfully to 600t.

3.2 August 1982 to October 1982

Following the failure of Pile 30D, piling was suspended and it was decided to redrive those piles which had not been capped. A substantial number of the piles failed to achieve their initial set on redriving. Further toe penetrations of up to 3.1m with an average of 0.6m were achieved before the set attained an acceptable value. Some of the piles were redriven a second, third and fourth time. In all 142 piles, i.e. 33% of the total, were redriven. Piling operations were held up for three months.

Two further load test failures were encountered on testing piles 38E and 42E, see Figure 4. Pile 42E had already been redriven once before the test. Both piles were founded on mudstone and the shape of the load settlement curve suggests a failure in end bearing. A successful load test to 750t was carried out on Pile 26D, which is also founded on mudstone. It was decided that all piles west of Bent No. 48 should be redriven to an empirically derived set of about 55 blows/50mm.

3.3 November 1982 to March 1983

Piling was restarted at the end of October 1982 on Bent No. 25. The piles were driven to an increased set of 75 blows/50mm, following a further review of the available records. Two redrives were necessary on many occasions. Further penetrations of up to 1.3m were recorded.

In November 1982 Balkan Piling Ltd. was instructed to carry out some dynamic tests ("Capwap" type) on selected piles to investigate this apparent loss of set and to check whether driving to a set of 75 blows/50mm would overstress the piles. The results of their work is discussed in Section 4.4. Successful compression tests were carried out on piles 19D and 4A to a load of 750t. Tension tests to 80t were successfully carried out on three raking piles.

4.1.2 Rock Type

The superficial deposits were found to be much as described in Section 2.2 above. However much more data was now available on the bedrock. It was possible to sub-divide the bedrock as follows:

Layer	Description	Thickness (m)
Upper Mudstone	Laminated mod. strong grey MUDSTONE	up to 8.3 proven
Sandstone Marker Bed	Medium bedded strong to very strong grey SANDSTONE	up to 2.6m proven
Lower Mudstone	Laminated mod. strong to strong grey MUDSTONE	1.4 to 3.8 proven
Lower Mudstone	Laminated mod. strong grey MUDSTONE	0.3 to 11.1 proven

Table 2: Moneypoint - Bedrock Description

Based on the bedrock type and the fracture state the area beneath the jetty was divided into 4 zones as follows:

Zone	Outcrop	Description
1.	Sandstone	Sandstone at rockhead or eroded and lower mudstone outcropping
2.	Upper Mudstone	Sandstone marker 0 to 4m below rockhead
3.	Upper Mudstone	Sandstone marker 4m to 8m below rockhead
4	Upper Mudstone	Sandstone marker more than 8m below rockhead

Table 3 : Moneypoint - Division of Jetty into Zones

The geological conditions are summarised on Figure 5. The overall dip of the bedrock is about 20° to the north. This overall dip is disturbed by a fault between Bent Nos 21 and 23 on the A line and at about Bent No. 30 on the D line. The sandstone marker horizon outcrops on the south east corner of the jetty.

4.1.3 Fracture State

Envelopes of RQD and fracture frequency (discontinuities per metre) are presented in Figure 6. The data is presented zone by zone and the plots are relative to the top of bedrock. The plots show a clear decrease in RQD and increase in fracture frequency from Zone 1 to Zone 4, that is up the geological succession. This deterioration in rock quality is particularly marked in the range of 2m to 3m below rockhead, which is the depth of most relevance to piling. For Zone 1, the depth below rockhead has little or no effect on the sandstones or lower mudstones.

COMPARISON OF ENVELOPES OF FRACTURE FREQUENCY
PLOTTED AGAINST DEPTH BELOW ROCKHEAD

COMPARISON OF ENVELOPES OF ROCK QUALITY DESIGNATION
PLOTTED AGAINST DEPTH BELOW ROCKHEAD

COMPARISON OF ENVELOPES OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH
PLOTTED AGAINST DEPTH BELOW ROCKHEAD

FIGURE 6 : ROCK QUALITY AND STRENGTH

4.1.4 Rock Strength

Envelopes of unconfined compressive strength versus depth below rockhead are presented on Figure 6. The plots show much variability, with only minor differences between the various zones.

The average unconfined compressive strength for the mudstone is about 20MN/m², compared to a value of 25MN/m² for the initial investigation, see Section 2.2. The strength of the sandstone was assessed at 100MN/m² as before.

A correlation between unconfined compressive strength and point load strength is also shown on Figure 7. It can be seen that, for tests on adjacent samples, $q_c = 27 \times I_s (50)$. This correlation number of 27 is somewhat larger than the value of 22 which would be expected from published data (ISRM, 1984, Ref. 4).

FIGURE 7 : CORRELATION BETWEEN MEASURED UNIAXIAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND AXIAL POINT LOAD INDEX I_s [50] FOR MUDSTONES

4.2 Penetration into Bedrock

From a study of more than 170 piles between Bent Nos 26 and 76 it would appear that the "problem" piles, that is those which experienced a substantial loss in set or achieved a large additional penetration when redriven, are generally in Zones 3 or 4, with a limited number in Zone 2. This is supported by the following result which was obtained for the initial pile driving:

Zone	Mean Penetration (m)
1.	0.1
2.	0.5
3.	1.0
4.	1.4

Table 4 : Moneypoint - Pile Penetration into Bedrock

Although there is some scatter in the results within each zone, the mean penetration tended to increase from Zone 1 to Zone 4, that is with increasing distance above the sandstone marker bed.

4.3 Failed Static Load Tests

The load test results for the three failed static load tests are shown on Figure 4. The figure includes a plot of settlement against load ratio P/P_u (ie. load over ultimate load). The curves for the three tests are similar, and indicate a very consistent elastic behaviour to a load of 500t. Yielding of the ground beneath the toe appears to have commenced at loads of between 500t and 550t. The figure suggests a linear characteristic up to a yield point corresponding to a load ratio of about 0.7. The curves are similar to those published by other authors for piles in clay, for example by Butler and Morton (1971, Ref. 5) and Patel (1992, Ref. 6) and may indicate that the piles are end bearing at least partly on the glacial overburden.

It is interesting also to compare the normalised depth of penetration L/D (ie depth of penetration over pile diameter) for the successful and unsuccessful tests as follows:

Pile No.	Zone	L/D	Test Result
4A	3	1.12	Passed
19D	4	2.52	Passed
26D	4	1.33	Passed
68D	1	n/a in sandstone	Passed
30D	4	0.49	Failed
38E	4	0.97	Failed
42E	4	0.87	Failed

Table 5 : Moneypoint - Results of Static Pile Load Tests

4.3 Cont...

It is possible to interpret the successful pile tests as those in which the L/D value is greater than unity. All of the piles which failed tests were located in Zone 4, see Figure 5.

Additional drillholes put down at the positions of two of the piles which failed indicated that rockhead varied considerably over small lateral distances. At Pile 30D two boreholes drilled approximately 1m apart indicated a difference in rockhead of 1.8m. Whereas the higher rockhead indicates an L/D value of 0.49, the lower rockhead corresponds to a level 1.2m below the toe. At Pile 38E three boreholes all located within 1m of the pile showed rockhead to vary by 1.53m. The highest rockhead indicates an L/D value of 0.97 and the lowest rockhead to be 0.35m below the pile toe.

It is possible therefore that the failure of the piles was due to the lack of contact or possibly only partial contact between the pile toe and bedrock. It was also concluded that rockhead may be locally sloping but that it is more probably stepped.

4.4 Dynamic Load Tests

Balken Piling Ltd. (BPL) carried out dynamic ("Capwap" type) tests on six piles in December 1982.

The following is a summary of the test results:

1. The measured energy of the hammer blow on the pile was on average 39% higher at the start of a redrive when compared to the end of the initial driving. This may account partly for the false set phenomenon.
2. The hammer was operating at an average about 37% efficiency. Diesel hammers would normally be expected to operate at an efficiency of about 70%.
3. The maximum driving stress recorded of 164N/mm² was only about 70% of the minimum yield stress for Grade 43A steel. Thus driving the piles to a set of over 75 blows/50mm would not cause them any damage.
4. On average 64% of the ultimate load capacity predicted by the "Capwap" analysis was due to skin friction. This most likely overestimates the true situation as the energy applied to the pile head would not be sufficient to mobilise much of the base resistance.
5. Ultimate skin friction value of 42kN/m² and 126kN/m² were estimated for the overburden and mudstone respectively.

4.5 Literature Review

A well known case involving a similar phenomenon to that observed at Moneypoint was reported by George, Sherrell and Tomlinson (1976, Ref. 7). They describe the installation of H piles into slaty mudstone for a bridge project at Teighnmouth, U.K. On redriving, the original set was not regained until the piles penetrated further distances into the mudstone of between a few centimetres and 4m. They suspected that stress relaxation of the shattered mudstone, exacerbated by the driving of adjacent piles, may have been the cause. The mudstone at Teighnmouth was somewhat weaker than that at Moneypoint and it also contained zones of soft clayey material up to 0.5m thick and thus may not be a good precedent.

Fleming et. al. (1992, Ref. 8) describe a site in highly fractured hard Mercia Mudstone (Keuper Marl) where tubular steel piles required several redrives at intervals of several days to eliminate deterioration in sets. They cited the delay in the dissipation of negative pore pressures induced by the driving as the cause.

4.5 Cont...

Thompson and Thompson (1985, Ref. 9) and Thompson (1992, Ref. 10) concluded that for a case involving piles driven into glacial tills in the US by diesel hammers, the "apparent relaxation" problem was due to operator variability. They found (and subsequently proved by "Capwap" testing) that on a redrive, once the engineer started to watch the pile driving more closely, the operator was more careful to set up the capblock, leads and hammer more accurately. This caused a "clean" blow and increased the driving energy. They also found that diesel hammers reach a maximum efficiency soon after starting and have a reduced energy after extended periods of hard driving. This was shown to be the case at Moneypoint, see Section 4.4.

Lehane and Jardine (1992, Ref. 11) reported on the development of negative pore pressures, caused by dilation, during the pushing of jacked piles into lodgement till at Cowden, Humberside. Jardine (1992, Ref. 12) suggested that this phenomenon accounted for the loss in driving resistance on redriving of some precast concrete piles driven into Dublin lodgement till at Tallaght (Armishaw and Bunni, 1992, Ref. 13). The authors of the latter paper felt that the phenomenon was most likely due to creep due to crushing of grains in the highly stressed zone around the pile shaft.

King et al. (1987, Ref. 14) report on a "false set" phenomenon encountered during the driving of the tubular steel piles for the replacement Redmond Bridge in Waterford, Ireland. They concluded the "false set" was due to the excess pore pressures developed in the glacial overburden during pile driving. They found that the excess pore pressures dissipated after 1 to 2 hours and then driving could recommence. They felt the problem could occur when the silt content of the material was in excess of 26%. The silt content of the glacial deposits at Moneypoint was also in the region of 26% suggesting similar phenomena could have occurred there.

5.0 MONEYPOINT JETTY - REMEDIAL ACTION

The remedial action taken by ESB comprised a review of the actual pile loads, a review of the "set" required during pile driving, and the specification of a limited number of extra piles.

The review of the jetty loading confirmed that the actual pile loads were somewhat less than the 600t estimated in the original design. The revised working loads were estimated to be of the order of 425t, with a maximum of 440t on Row A, caused by the three unloaders working between the west and the centre strongpoint.

For all uncapped piles a new regime of pile "sets" and redrive "sets" was arrived at empirically by examining all of the driving records and pile test results. It was concluded that if the piles were driven to the sets detailed below they would have a factor of safety of about 1.6. It was felt that a factor of safety of 2.0 could not be achieved because of the fractured nature of the rock. The behaviour of the three failed pile tests was linear to a minimum load of 425t. The settlements recorded at this load were less than 15mm and were thus concluded tolerable. It was therefore concluded that with the new regime of pile driving in place the piles could satisfactorily carry the required loading. (This is equivalent to applying a safety margin of 1.15 to the load factor of 0.7 in the Butler and Morton approach, 1971, Ref 5).

Piles west of Bent No. 48 were driven and redriven to a set of 55 blows/50mm and those west of Bent No. 25 were driven to a set of 75 blows/50mm, following a further review of the available records.

A number of piles between the eastern and central strong-points were a source of worry as they had been capped and could not be redriven. It was decided to drive 8 No. extra piles between Bent Nos 48 and 50 and Bent Nos 54 and 56. It was cheaper to install the extra piles rather than try to test the capped piles.

6.0 Moneypoint Jetty - Discussion on Reasons for Piling Difficulties

6.1 False Set Phenomenon

The following conclusions can be made on the false set phenomenon at Moneypoint:-

- The difficulties were mostly encountered in Zone 4, where the greatest penetration was recorded on initial driving and where the mudstones of poorest quality are present.
- It is most likely that the action of driving the piles into the heavily jointed mudstone shattered the rock into small pieces. These pieces were wedged tightly between the pile and the intact bedrock during driving. Following the driving some stress relief could have taken place resulting in the reduction in the skin friction on the pile.
- The false set may be partly due to the increase in available driving energy of the hammer at the start of re-driving.
- The delay in the dissipation of negative pore pressures which developed in the clayey glacial overburden during pile driving may have also contributed to the false set phenomenon.

6.2 Load Test Failures

It would seem that the load test failures were caused by failure of the piles in end bearing. It is possible that these failures occurred because the full area of the pile was not bearing on rock of satisfactory quality or possibly partly bearing on the glacial deposits. It is interesting to note, however, that all of the failures took place in Zone 4 and that the penetration into bedrock to diameter (L/D) ratio was less than 1.0 for the failed piles and greater than 1.0 for the successful pile tests.

6.3 Pile Driving and Pile Driving Formulae

The Moneypoint experience confirms the widely held opinion that pile driving formulae are not a reliable means of determining ultimate pile capacity.

This case history emphasises the importance of the choice of hammer for pile driving and the importance of maintaining the efficiency of the hammer during the works.

The use of "Capwap" during preliminary pile tests would much enhance an understanding of the hammer behaviour and help in the final choice of hammer.

7.0 Keelbeg Pier - Investigation and Design

7.1 Investigation

An investigation of the pier site for the Department of the Marine was carried out by Site Investigations Ltd. (SIL) in 1990. This investigation comprised 49 No. shell and auger holes some of which were extended by rotary coring. ESBI were appointed to design the pier structure in 1993. It was decided that insufficient information existed on the bedrock and a further investigation comprising five rotary cored boreholes was drilled by Hilliard Ltd. and logged by Carraigex Ltd. in September 1993. A view of the pier during piling operations is shown on Figure 8.

FIGURE 8 : VIEW OF KEELBEG PIER DURING PILING WORKS

7.2 Geology

The investigations proved the following succession of strata:

Stratum	Thickness (m)
Estuarine Deposits (Soft grey organic silt)	Zero to 13.8. Typically 6
Glacial Deposits (Dense coarse sand and gravel)	1 - 8
Bedrock	7.1 max. proven.

Table 6 : Keelbeg - Geology

The bedrock comprised a mixture of moderately strong and strong, green, thinly laminated, slightly weathered sandstone and moderately weak, pale green, laminated moderately weathered, mudstone. The location of the bedrock type sand derived from the rock cores and inspection of nearby outcrops, as well as contours of the top of the bedrock, are shown on the site plan in Figure 9. Sandstone was encountered in three of the five boreholes, mudstone in one and a mudstone/sandstone combination in the fifth.

7.2 Cont..

The sandstone has an average RQD of 34% and had an average of 20 fractures per metre. The mudstone had an average RQD of 61% and 13 fractures per metre. The sandstone and mudstone had average unconfined compressive strength values of 44MN/m² and 16MN/m² respectively. The mudstone at Keelbeg is therefore weaker but has approximately the same number of discontinuities, as that of Zone 4 at Moneypoint.

FIGURE 9 : KEELBEG PIER LAYOUT SHOWING GEOLOGY

7.3 Design of Pile Foundations

The experience gained at Moneypoint was applied in the design of the piles at Keelbeg as follows:

- It was specified that the piles should be driven at least to rockhead level in the sandstone areas and it was envisaged that a penetration ratio, L/D , of 1.0 would be achieved in the mudstone areas.
- A static design calculation was carried out assuming that all of the applied load would be taken in end bearing on the weaker mudstone rock. The ultimate end bearing capacity was again taken as $6 \times UCS$ after Rehnman and Broms (1971, Ref. 2).
- A programme of redrives was specified. It was specified that the construction of the pile caps and jetty deck should be phased such that it would be possible to redrive a pile up to 6 weeks after the initial driving.

7.4 Jetty Structure

Keelbeg Pier is intended for use by fishing vessels. It is 150m x 12m in plan and is supported on 96 No. 660mm diameter, 20m long, open ended tubular steel piles. The piles have a wall thickness of 22mm and are formed of Grade 60 steel. A view of the jetty is shown on Figure 8 and the plan layout of the jetty is shown on Figure 9.

The pier is designed to absorb lateral loads from 80t(dwt) fishing vessels and a vertical live loads of 20kN/m².

The piles were designed for a working load of 150t i.e. a factor of safety of about 2.5 was applied to the Rehnman and Broms calculation.

8.0 Keelbeg Pier - Piling Construction

Some driving trials were carried out at the beginning of the contract to establish the pile lengths which would be required and to determine a guide "set" which could be used to act as a control during pile driving.

The piling was successfully carried out between October 1993 and January 1994. The piles were driven using a Delmag D22 Diesel hammer which has a weight of 2,200kg and a nominal rated energy per blow of 5,500kgm. at 40-60 blows per minute. The ram to pile weight ratio was about 0.4. The penetration resistance was generally negligible in the estuarine deposits, 10 to 15 blows per 150mm in the glacial gravels deposits and increased rapidly to a set of 50 blows per 50mm in the bedrock. Penetration ratios, L/D, of 1 to 2 and 1 to 6 were generally achieved in the sandstone and mudstone respectively.

The piles were redriven, sometimes up to 3 times, at periods of up to 6 weeks after the initial driving. The final set achieved during the initial driving was reestablished immediately on redriving in each case.

Successful static pile test were carried out on pile 1C and 13A. The behaviour of the piles was elastic up to the test load of 240t.

Dynamic tests ("Capwap" type) were carried out on 11 No. piles. The tests confirmed the working pile capacity of 150t in each case. The test results also suggested that an average of 25% of the ultimate load capacity was due to skin friction. Again this is likely to underestimate the true situation as the impact of the piling hammer would not be able to mobilise the full end bearing resistance of the piles.

The diesel hammer was shown to operate at an average efficiency of 28%, which again is a very low value. The "Capwap" tests were carried out as restrrike tests on previously installed piles. As the set was reestablished immediately on redriving there was no opportunity to measure the possible drop off in hammer efficiency during driving.

9.0 Conclusions

A description has been given of some difficulties encountered during the installation of tubular steel piles into laminated mudstones in south west Ireland. The possible reasons for the development of the false set phenomenon at Moneypoint were:

- stress relaxation in the shattered mudstone.
- increase in available energy at the start of redriving when compared to the end of driving,
- delay in the dissipation of negative pore water pressures in the clayey glacial overburden,

The phenomenon was not encountered at Keelbeg even though the mudstone has a similar fracture state to that at Moneypoint, albeit a much larger hammer had been used there. The glacial material at Keelbeg is predominantly granular. This gives some support to the possibility that the problems at Moneypoint were at least partly caused by the delay in the dissipation of negative pore pressures.

9.0 Cont..

It was shown that the three pile test failures were either due to inadequate penetration of the piles into the bedrock.

Moneypoint jetty has now performed well for almost 10 years. Up to a maximum of 2.25 million tonnes of coal have been off loaded at the jetty each year.

The experiences emphasise the importance of detailed site investigation to establish bedrock level, variability and the quality of the bedrock. It was also shown that care should be taken when establishing pile capacity from conventional "static or "dynamic" pile driving formulae. The pile design should take into consideration the likely behaviour of the piles during the initial driving and redriving.

10.0 Acknowledgements

The permission of Mr. Bart Moriarty, Station Manager, ESB, Moneypoint and Dr. Gerard Farrell, Chief Engineer, Department of the Marine to publish the material contained in this paper is gratefully acknowledged. The assistance of my colleagues in ESBI, particularly Mr. Michael Gibbons and Mr Dick O'Flaherty, for reviewing the paper is also acknowledged.

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